

Fostering sustainable soil management practices across Europe (i-SoMPE)

Martina Kittinger, Adelheid Spiegel, Taru Sandén, Olivier Heller, Irene Criscuoli and Frédéric Vanwindekens

- i-SoMPE mapped sustainable soil practices and built an interactive website showing adoption across Europe.
- Adoption is limited by knowledge gaps, financial risks, cultural barriers and biophysical constraints—regional solutions are needed.
- Farmer–advisor–researcher networks can boost knowledge sharing and uptake.
- Markets and financial incentives for soil-friendly products can drive investment and farmer interest.

INTRODUCTION

Sustainable agricultural soil management practices are key to restore, maintain and improve soil health. Several sustainable soil management practices exist all over Europe. Applying such techniques is also important with regard to climate change.

The i-SoMPE project compiled an inventory of soil-improving management practices relevant to European conditions and used a survey among soil scientists to assess the current and potential adoption of these practices in Europe. Where available, the survey results were compared to available data from EUROSTAT. The research carried out aimed to assess the level of adoption of sustainable soil management practices and to identify obstacles hindering this adoption.

DESCRIPTION OF THE ISSUE

Introducing innovative soil management practices and alternative farming techniques in intensive agricultural systems can help to enhance agroecosystem resilience to soil threats or environmental stress and to preserve soils from degradation.

Many farmers are open to introduce sustainable management practices to make their farms more climate-smart and sustainable. However, to do so farmers need practice specific know-how. Moreover, innovative technical solutions (e.g., precision farming) are often linked to investments that are not affordable to most farmers. Additional barriers that limit the application of new practices by farmers include climatic constraints, financial risks, or socio-cultural lock-ins.

The i-SoMPE survey revealed that the adoption of most sustainable soil management practices was either low or heterogenous across Europe (see Figure 1 for cover cropping and reduced tillage). This finding implies that (i) there is potential for increased adoption of sustainable soil management practices and (ii) that region-specific limitations to adoption exist. In order to assess the potential and foster the adoption of soil-improving management practices, it is necessary to know (i) the current levels of adoption of the practices, and overcome (ii) the social, technical and economic barriers influencing their adoption and (iii) reduce their biophysical limitations by innovation (Figure 2).

Figure 1 (a, b): Adoption level of cover cropping (a) and reduced tillage (b) in Europe at NUTS2 level, based on EUROSTAT data (Source: Heller et al., 2024).

Figure 2: The adoption of a practice may increase without targeted political or technological actions until the further spread of the practice is hampered either by socio-technical barriers or biophysical limits (e.g. climate, soil properties or slope). The socio-technical and economic barriers can be overcome (dashed curve) through changes in policies or utilization of other instruments (e.g., provision of knowledge, establishment of farmer-advisor-researcher networks, increased availability of practice-specific machinery, or financial incentives). Whereas innovation, research and development (e.g., new cultivars, new implements) are needed to move the bio-physical limits and expand the potential area of adoption to a new biophysical limit (dotted curve)- (Source: Heller et al., 2024)

KEY MESSAGES FOR POLICY MAKERS

Recommendation One: Support knowledge networks and information

To overcome soil threats and challenges it is essential to foster knowledge sharing and experience (e.g., organized field visits) for exchange between stakeholders (farmers, advisors, policy makers and researchers). Supporting networks of knowledge brokers (innovative farmers, farmer organizations, advisors, researchers) and improving the science-practice interface (e.g., establishing living labs) enhances knowledge availability to farmers.

Recommendation Two: Implement a region-specific approach to foster the adoption of sustainable soil management

Many soil-improving management practices exist but are only adopted on a low level and/or heterogeneously across Europe. Thus, a region-specific approach is needed to identify and overcome socio-technical and economic barriers to the adoption of sustainable soil management practices (Figure 2). At EU and member states level appropriate guidelines, legislation, smoothly running knowledge networks and interaction between stakeholders are recommended. Furthermore, the site-specific impacts of soil management practices need further evaluation to ensure soil health benefits and reduce trade-offs such as yield reduction, lower farm profitability or additional greenhouse gas emissions.

Recommendation Three: Creating markets for products from sustainably managed soils

Currently, no market exists for agricultural products that are produced by applying sustainable soil management practices (beyond the organic market). Therefore, it is essential to create markets for products that stem from sustainable soil management practices (e.g., by labelling). Together with other financial incentives, such markets would stimulate farmers to make investments (e.g., in new technology or know-how).

SUPPORTING POLICY

The new Common Agricultural Policy (CAP 2023-2027, Reg. EU 2021/2116) targets sustainable soil management both in the first pillar, through conditionality and voluntary eco-schemes and in the second pillar via agro-environmental measures and investment support. Moreover, strategies for adaptation to climate change are acknowledged in the CAP Strategic Plans (CSPs). However, CAP interventions are still lacking detailed guidance for implementation and a long-term strategy is not clearly outlined (Chartier et al., 2023). However, within the CAP low financial support (0.1% - 2.7% of the CAP budget across CSPs) is allocated to knowledge related interventions (e.g., training, advice), limiting the exchange of knowledge (Chartier et al., 2023). To further improve the CAP, empirical research is needed to estimate the impact of policy measures and a good science-based communication is needed to foster implementation and the collaboration among all stakeholders (Mennig, 2024). In this framework, the i-SoMPE project, with its insights, can contribute to this improvement by complementing the interventions of the CAP in assessing and implementing sustainable soil management practices.

METHODOLOGY

53 soil management practices, addressing at least one soil challenge, were collected in a stock-take carried out in 2021 and reported in an online inventory (<https://shinyapp.cra.wallonie.be/isompe-inventory/>). The inventory includes a general description of the soil management practice, an estimate of the potential area of implementation

(considering climate, site and soil factors, land use and farming system) as well as the impacts of the practice on the soil challenges.

Qualitative interviews with conservation agriculture experts were conducted to explore the importance of socio-technical aspects for the adoption of the soil management practice.

REFERENCES

- Chartier et al., (2023). European Commission: Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development, Mapping and analysis of CAP strategic plans – Assessment of joint efforts for 2023-2027 – Executive summary. Publications Office of the European Union, 2023, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2762/12295>
- Heller et al. (2024). Towards enhanced adoption of soil-improving management practices in Europe. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 75(2), e13483. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13483>
- Keesstra et al. (2023). European agricultural soil management: Towards climate-smart and sustainability, knowledge needs and research approaches. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 75(1), e13437. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13437>
- Mennig, P. A never-ending story of reforms: on the wicked nature of the Common Agricultural Policy. *npj Sustain. Agric.* **2**, 20 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44264-024-00027-z>
- Thorsøe et al. (2023). Sustainable soil management: Soil knowledge use and gaps in Europe. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 74(6), e13439. <https://bsssjournals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/ejss.13439>

